

THE ROLE OF FILM AND MUSIC FESTIVALS IN RELATION BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND TURKMENISTAN

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Abstract The Uzbek and Turkmen peoples have lived with common goals as close friends, friendly neighbors, and strategic partners since time immemorial. Therefore, the roots of the relations between the two countries go back to a long history and are built on the basis of mutual respect and trust. Uzbek and Turkmen peoples have been drinking water from the same river for a long time and lived peacefully and harmoniously. Our peoples are united by a common history, common culture and values, similar language and customs. This closeness is the basis of strong cooperation between our countries.

Keywords Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, neighbour, region, cooperation, Central Asia, political, history.

Festivals between two countries

It is known that interstate cultural relations are most clearly manifested within the framework of international festivals. for example, in Uzbekistan alone "Sharq Taronalari" music festival (since 1997), International Status Art Conference (since 2018), International Festival of Giving Art (since 2019), International Crafts Festival (since 2019), "Great Silk way" international folk music festival (from 2019)In Kazakhstan, it has become a tradition to hold a number of international cultural festivals, such as "Voice of Asia", "Korqut and Great Steppe Song" folklore music art festival (since 2006)

On August 28-29, 1997, the International Music Festival "Sharq Taronalari" and the International Conference on "Commonality of Music Art of Eastern Peoples" were

held in Samarkand. The festival was held for the first time in 1997, and 267 singers, musicians and honored guests from 31 countries and 2 international organizations took part in it.

Uzbekistan participated as a host and on a separate list. About the 1999 "Sharq Taronalari" international music festival, the opinion of the Minister of Culture of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Polat Bulbul, and Gi Doga, Secretary General of the International Council of UNESCO, this event is Eastern and whole. It shows that cultural dialogue is of great importance in the fraternization of the peoples of the world.

The events of the 2003 "Sharq Taronalari" festival were mainly in three directions: 1. Competition of the best national songs: 2. Scientific and creative conferences: 3. The gala was held in the form of a concert. Souvenirs and cash prizes were awarded to the winners. In 2017, the "Sharq Taronalari" festival was visited by participants from 56 countries, which means that its prestige is growing more and more.

Representatives of Turkmenistan are also successfully participating in the "Sharq Taronalari" international music festival. At the 7th international music festival held in 2009, where more than 260 musicians and singers from 47 countries participated, L. Begnazarova from Turkmenistan won the Grand Prix "Sharq taronalari" became the owner.

In short, the interest in this festival, which has taken a worthy place in the world community, is increasing every year. Such a large-scale event is an honor for any country, and at the same time, it also places a great responsibility on the world community. The fact that the festival is included among UNESCO's international cultural events shows its high political and spiritual level, of course. This is widely recognized by the world community. For example, French musicologist Olive Delsal admits that such a comprehensive conference shows the country's openness to intercultural dialogue and its support for its further strengthening.

On April 7-12, 2008, the chamber orchestra "Soloists of Uzbekistan" from our country took part in the festival "Turkmenistan: the spiritual treasure of human musical art" held in Ashgabat

According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyov on November 1, 2018, the International Festival of the Art of Giving, which was held for the first time in the city of Termiz on April 5-10, 2019, was widely recognized as a major international cultural event. as Shavkat Mirziyov noted, "It is well known to all of us that the priceless masterpieces of culture created by humanity, first of all, are expressed in the folklore art of any nation. The art of giving, which expresses the national identity of different peoples, their language and way of life, traditions and customs, is valuable for all of us as an integral part of universal culture. Performers, folklorists, experts from 74 countries, as well as honored guests from Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Afghanistan participated in this festival held under the auspices of UNESCO. within the framework of the festival, events such as an international scientific-practical conference, an exhibition of artisans, and a competition of cooks called "Uzbek cuisine" were held. In addition to handicrafts, an exhibition of national songs and costumes, works of applied and visual arts, sculpture, art and documentary films, books, albums, and photographs was organized at the folk fairs held within the framework of the conference

In recent years, special attention is being paid to the art of baksheesh at the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. in particular, on May 14, 2019, according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further develop the art of philanthropy", the main tasks of the Republican Art Center of philanthropy in the city of Termiz are international in the field of philanthropy issues of strengthening cooperation, establishing mutual exchange of experience in this regard, including the organization of various international conferences, competitions, concerts and master classes

Cultural-educational tourism route in Samarkand includes "Sharq Taronalari" international music festival, folklore group concerts at Sherdor and Mirzo Ulug'bek madrasas, performances of "Chavqi", "Beshkarsak", "Sarbozi" folk groups in districts, 3D show in Registon, "El -heritage" nationalcultural theater, "Uloq-kopchasi" games, saying alla, showing the rituals of cradling a baby were added. Also, new - educational tourism is introduced, the most popular of which is the Imam Bukhari International Scientific Research Center and the School of Hadith Science. It is worth noting that these festivals are held not only in Samarkand, but also in other districts and cities, which paves the way for the development of tourism in all regions of the region

In Bukhara, one of the cradles of ancient civilizations in the region, in order to increase the potential of tourism, the annual "Silk and Spices" festival, "Pilov sale", "Melon sale", scientific-practical conference dedicated to the birth of Ibn Sina for local and foreign tourists, "NationalEvents such as the "Traditions" festival are held regularly. We are participating in this festival, which took place on May 5, 2015, for the second time - says Jacques-Henri Els, Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary of France to our country. - Such events bring special pleasure to a person. your national dishes are diverse. Those who have tasted them rate their taste highly. We are happy about it. When the time comes, it is worth mentioning that the delicacies prepared in the Uzbek kitchen are also distinguished by their color and delicacy. for example, your national dishes such as pilaf, manti, somsa are famous all over the world. The open-mindedness, sweet-talking and hospitality of your people deserve special recognition. The ambassador admits that I am happy that I am working in such a wonderful country

In particular, on May 26-28, 2016, the XV International "Silk and Spices" festival and within its framework "Attracting foreign investments, modern technologies and innovative projects to Bukhara - development of the tourism sector, renewal of the service system and internationally recognized culturalan international scientific and practical conference was held on .trade of silk fabrics and spices was organized as

part of the event. Masters of Gijduvan pottery, Bukhara brass engraving, silk carpet, embroidery, and goldsmith schools held skill classes. a fine and practical art gallery, an exhibition of photographers, and a display of national costumes were organized. A national games competition and a dinner were held.

During the visit of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to Kashkadarya region on December 13-14, 2018, Shahrisabz was declared the "City of Festivals" in order to turn Shahrisabz into one of the major tourism centers and increase the tourism potential of the region. based on this, a plan of events and festivals held throughout the year was developed in cooperation with relevant ministries and agencies, local governments. the city has enough natural opportunities for the development of ecotourism, extreme tourism, ethnotourism, gastronomic tourism, pilgrimage tourism. the fact that the highest peak and the largest glacier in our country are in the Hisar mountain ranges, the fossilized traces of dinosaurs have been preserved in the village of Tashkurgan, and the proximity of the Amir Temur cave, rich in circinoates, to Shahrisabz, provide an opportunity for the development of the above types of tourism. in particular, only in the city of Shahrisabz, the International Status Festival, the International Festival of National Costumes, the folk games of kupkari and wrestling are held on the days of Navruz national holiday. Also, the festival "Shahrisabz - a place of artisans", the music festival "Shahrisabz music dance", the eco-festival "Hisar mountains", and the agrotourism festival "Anor" will be organized. By the way, every year on February 1-8, Shahrisabz hosts a tourist area. industry specialists, tour operators, foreign experts will participate in it and discuss the current issues of increasing and promoting the tourism potential of Uzbekistan.

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